

ADDRESSING THE COMPLEXITIES: ENSURING DOPING CONTROL IN SPORTS**Khudoyqulova Zulfizar Sayfiddin qizi****Sports Law Master's student of the
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Abstract: Doping in sports continues to pose a significant challenge, tarnishing the integrity and fairness of athletic competitions. As athletes strive for excellence, the temptation to gain a competitive edge through prohibited substances or methods persists. To combat this issue, stringent measures and innovative strategies are imperative to maintain a level playing field and safeguard the spirit of fair play in sports. This article discusses some of the challenges involved in ensuring doping control in professional sports, including the methods used to establish doping control and the testing procedure, as well as worldwide coordination and collaboration to strengthen international relationships in doping control.

Key words: doping, doping control, testing procedure, methods, athlete education, awareness of athletes, technological challenges, ethical considerations, advanced technology.

Doping, a practice as old as competitive sports itself, continues to challenge the integrity and fairness of athletic competitions worldwide. Despite stringent regulations and advancements in testing methodologies, the battle against doping remains an ongoing struggle. The issues surrounding ensuring doping control in sports are multifaceted and require a comprehensive approach. Doping refers to the use of performance-enhancing drugs or methods that contravene the rules and regulations set forth by sports governing bodies. It encompasses various substances, from anabolic steroids to stimulants and blood doping, all of which can artificially enhance an athlete's performance.

Anti-doping agencies are continually adapting their testing methods to keep up with these evolving techniques. They employ more advanced detection methods, including longitudinal testing (tracking changes in an athlete's biomarkers over time), intelligence gathering, and implementing biological passports to monitor athletes' profiles for any unusual changes that might indicate doping.

Despite these advancements in detection, staying ahead of doping practices remains a challenge due to the constant evolution of both doping methods and the technology used to detect them.

Evolving Methods of Doping. Advancements in science and technology have led to the development of new, harder-to-detect doping substances and methods. Athletes and their support teams continually seek ways to stay ahead of anti-doping agencies, requiring constant vigilance and adaptation in testing procedures.

The methods of doping have evolved significantly over the years, driven by advancements in technology, medicine, and the quest to evade detection. Some of the evolving methods include:

Designer Drugs: These are synthetic substances created to mimic the effects of banned performance-enhancing drugs while attempting to avoid detection by anti-doping tests.

They're designed to be structurally similar to banned substances but different enough to evade standard testing.¹

Gene Doping: This involves manipulating genes to enhance athletic performance. It's a cutting-edge technique that aims to modify genes to produce specific proteins or hormones that enhance strength, endurance, or other desired traits. Detecting gene doping remains a significant challenge for anti-doping agencies.²

Microdosing: Athletes may use small, frequent doses of performance-enhancing substances, such as steroids or erythropoietin (EPO), in amounts that are difficult to detect in standard tests. This method aims to gain the benefits of doping while minimizing the risk of being caught. "Smaller amounts are being taken in the hope that they will be undetectable," said David Howman, director general of the World Anti-Doping Agency (WADA), in an interview with the DPA.³ **Blood Doping:** This involves increasing the number of red blood cells in the body to enhance oxygen-carrying capacity. Techniques like blood transfusions or using drugs like EPO stimulate the production of red blood cells, improving endurance. Athletes may now use more sophisticated methods to manipulate their blood profiles, making detection more challenging.⁴ **Masking Agents:** These substances are used to hide the presence of banned substances or manipulate test results. They can dilute urine, change its pH, or interfere with the detection of prohibited drugs. Substances suitable for this purpose are therefore included in the Prohibited List of the WADA.⁵

However, what would be the solution to prevent athletes from using those so-called "evolving methods".

First solution would be - Athlete Education and Awareness.

Educating athletes about the risks and consequences of doping is crucial. Some may inadvertently consume banned substances due to ignorance or lack of understanding. Robust educational programs should emphasize the importance of clean competition and the severe penalties associated with doping violations. Any anti-doping programme must include education. The 2021 Code's introduction includes education on the avoidance of purposeful and inadvertent doping, as well as deterrent, detection, enforcement, and the rule of law. On January 1, 2021, the first International Standard for Education (ISE) went into effect. The ISE specifies the educational qualifications that Code Signatories must satisfy.⁶ According to the World Anti-Doping Agency's International Standard for Education, national and international

¹ Teale, P & Scarth, James & Hudson, S.. (2012). Impact of the emergence of designer drugs upon sports doping testing. *Bioanalysis*. 4. 71-88. 10.4155/bio.11.291.

² *Biol Sport*. 2014 Dec; 31(4): 251–259. Published online 2014 Sep 12. doi: [10.5604/20831862.1120931](https://doi.org/10.5604/20831862.1120931)

³ D. (2012, August 1). *Micro-dosing: the new trend in sports doping*. The Hindu.

<https://www.thehindu.com/sport/other-sports/microdosing-the-new-trend-in-sports-doping/article3710793.ece>

⁴ Horwath, H., & Horwath, H. (2020, January 3). *Blood Doping and EPO: An Anti-Doping FAQ* | USADA. U.S. Anti-Doping Agency (USADA). <https://www.usada.org/spirit-of-sport/education/blood-doping-epo-faq/>

⁵ *S5 Diuretics and other masking agents* | SSI. (n.d.). S5 Diuretics and Other Masking Agents | SSI.

<https://www.sportintegrity.ch/en/anti-doping/prevention/education/mobile-lesson/s5-diuretics#:~:text=Definition,Prohibited%20List%20of%20the%20WADA.>

⁶ *Education and Training*. (n.d.). World Anti Doping Agency. <https://www.wada-ama.org/en/what-we-do/education-and-training>

sports bodies must review their education initiatives. They responded to this request by investigating the efficacy of a national anti-doping system.⁷

In the ongoing fight against doping in sports, testing accuracy and reliability are also critical. Ensuring the accuracy and reliability of doping tests is paramount. False positives or erroneous results can tarnish an athlete's reputation irreparably. Continuous improvement and validation of testing methods are necessary to maintain credibility and fairness.⁸ However, there are some types of tests, which put the credibility of the findings of the anti-doping agencies. There is a non-threshold tests that lack precise and statistical limits of decision that definitively determine whether test findings should be regarded as positive or negative. Such tests can be deemed positive regardless of the amount of the drug under consideration, as long as it can be identified with adequate accuracy.⁹ The case involving German biathlete Evi Sachenbacher Stehle is an excellent illustration of what might happen when there is no definitive threshold. Grigoriy Rodchenkov, the chief of the Moscow laboratory, subsequently confessed in his book that, given the low dose of the drug, he would not have pursued the case. However, because the laboratory required some positive findings, in part because Russian athletes with positive tests were not disclosed, he classified this test as positive. Sachenbacher Stehle was initially banned for two years, most likely for drinking contaminated tea.¹⁰

Thirdly, Enforcement and Penalties. Consistent enforcement of anti-doping regulations across all sports and regions is essential. Penalties for doping violations must be stringent enough to deter athletes and their entourage from engaging in such practices. Fair and transparent processes for hearings and appeals are also critical to maintain trust in the system. Athletes must ensure that they compete in their sports fairly and that they maintain their activities as clean as possible. As Paragraph 2.1 of the Article 2 of the WADA Code stipulates "It is the Athletes' personal duty to ensure that no Prohibited Substance enters their bodies. Athletes are responsible for any Prohibited Substance or its Metabolites or Markers found to be present in their Samples."¹¹ Nonetheless, the Anti-Doping Organisations have the responsibility of determining whether an anti-doping rule infringement occurred. In the worst-case scenario, if athletes found guilty of breaching anti-doping rules they will face serious legal consequences. Article 10 of the WADA Code strictly establishes what sanctions could be imposed if any athlete is found in violation of anti-doping rules, as it includes types of sanctions such as disqualification of results in the event during which an anti-doping rule

⁷ Philip Hurst, Ailish King, Kelly Massey, Maria Kavussanu, Christopher Ring, A national anti-doping education programme reduces doping susceptibility in British athletes, *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, Volume 69, 2023, 102512, ISSN 1469 0292, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2023.102512>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S146902922300136X>)

⁸ Stanger, Nicholas & Whitaker, Lisa & Backhouse, Susan. (2020). Testing the validity and reliability of the doping willingness in sport scale. *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*. 30. 10.1111/sms.13683.

⁹ Nissen-Meyer, J., Skotland, T., & Boye, E. (2022, February 14). *Are doping tests in sports trustworthy?* *EMBO Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.15252/embr.202154431>

¹⁰ *Sachenbacher-Stehle Case Raises Questions about Supplement Use and Safety – FasterSkier.com*. (n.d.). <https://fasterskier.com/2014/07/sachenbacher-stehle-case-raises-questions-about-supplement-use-and-safety/>

¹¹ Paragraph 2.1. of the Article 2 of the WADA Code 2023, https://www.wada-ama.org/sites/default/files/resources/files/2021_wada_code.pdf

violation occurs, ineligibility for presence, use or attempted use or possession of a prohibited substance or prohibited methods.¹²

Moreover, funding and resources are of a great importance. Adequate funding and resources are required to conduct thorough testing and research into new doping substances and techniques. Lack of financial support can undermine anti-doping efforts, allowing gaps that can be exploited by those seeking to cheat.

We also have to consider global coordination and cooperation while taking all measures to avoid athletes from using prohibited substances. Doping is a global issue that transcends borders. International cooperation among sports organizations, governments, and anti-doping agencies is crucial. Harmonizing anti-doping efforts, sharing information, and establishing unified standards can strengthen the fight against doping. Europol and the World Anti-Doping Agency have signed a Memorandum of understanding to reinforce their cooperation in the fight against the doping in sports. The main purpose behind this Memorandum of understanding was to stop the illegal production and distribution of doping substances.¹³ Furthermore, it must be noted that several of the governments formed global international cooperation. There was an International Convention against Doping in Sport, which was entered into by the 191 states, and signed at the General Conference of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, referred to as "UNESCO", meeting in Paris, from 3 to 21 October 2005, at its 33rd session. The Convention's objective is to encourage the prevention and combat against doping in sports, with the goal of eventually eliminating it.

Enhancing global coordination involves fostering partnerships among governments, sports organizations, scientific communities, and law enforcement agencies. Sharing information, best practices, and resources across borders strengthens the fight against doping. International cooperation in intelligence sharing, joint investigations, and the implementation of uniform sanctions for offenders are vital components of this collaborative endeavor.

Furthermore, promoting a culture of clean sport goes beyond mere rule enforcement. It requires comprehensive education programs that instill values of integrity and fair play from grassroots levels to elite competitions. Athletes, coaches, and support staff need to be empowered with knowledge about the dangers of doping, ethical decision-making, and the importance of upholding the spirit of sportsmanship.

Ethical Considerations.

Debates surrounding the use of certain substances for therapeutic purposes and the line between legitimate medical treatment and unfair performance enhancement add complexity to anti-doping policies. Balancing athlete health needs with maintaining a level playing field requires careful ethical deliberation.

Doping in sports raises numerous ethical considerations that touch on fairness, health, and the essence of competition. Here are some key ethical aspects:

¹² Ibid, at 63-65

¹³ *Europol and the World Anti-Doping Agency to tackle doping together* | Europol. (n.d.). Europol.

<https://www.europol.europa.eu/media-press/newsroom/news/europol-and-world-anti-doping-agency-to-tackle-doping-together>

Fair Play: Doping violates the principle of fair play, giving an unfair advantage to athletes who use performance-enhancing substances over those who compete clean. It undermines the integrity of sports competitions, as success becomes less about skill, training, and natural ability and more about who can access and use the most effective substances.¹⁴

Health Risks: Doping often involves using substances that can have severe health consequences. Athletes might prioritize short-term performance gains over long-term health, potentially leading to irreversible damage or life-threatening conditions. This raises ethical questions about whether it's justifiable to compromise health for success in sports.¹⁵

Equality: Doping can widen the gap between athletes from affluent backgrounds who might have better access to advanced doping techniques, substances, or sophisticated medical supervision and those who lack these resources.¹⁶ This socioeconomic inequality contradicts the principles of equal opportunity in sports.

So, what legal implications do doping violations have for athletes?

Violation of Anti-Doping Regulations.

At the heart of the legal ramifications of doping lies the violation of anti-doping regulations established by international and national sporting bodies such as the World Anti-Doping Agency (WADA) and various sports federations. Athletes who test positive for banned substances face sanctions ranging from suspensions to lifetime bans, depending on the severity and frequency of the offense. These penalties are not merely sporting but carry significant legal weight, often subject to appeals and legal challenges.

Criminal Implications.

In some jurisdictions, doping may also have criminal implications. The distribution and use of certain banned substances could constitute offenses under controlled substances laws, leading to criminal charges against athletes, coaches, or even medical personnel involved in supplying or administering these substances. For instance, cases involving the distribution of steroids or other prohibited drugs may lead to criminal investigations and prosecutions. Jacek Potulski argues that even if the regulations of the sports federations establish the fight against the use of prohibited substances, legislation of some of the countries still lack the concept of criminal liability for doping in sport. He points to the importance of the Act, which must be adopted in every country and provides some expert opinions taking into consideration the Act of 21 April 2017 on combating doping in sport of Poland. Nonetheless, he is adamant that the Act of 6 September 2001 –Pharmaceutical Law is instrumental in establishing the criminal liability for doping in sport.¹⁷

Contractual Obligations.

Athletes often sign contracts with sports organizations, sponsors, and endorsements that contain clauses related to doping. A positive doping test could result in breaches of these contractual obligations, leading to financial penalties, termination of contracts, or legal

¹⁴ Levente Nagy, Sports and the Ethical Implications of Performance Enhancing Substances, <https://trivent-publishing.eu/img/cms/14-%20Levente%20Nagy.pdf>

¹⁵ A.M. Fadli, A.F. Idham, A.I. Nugraha, M.F. Dongoran, Effects of doping on physical and mental health of sports athletes, *Enfermería Clínica*, Volume 30, Supplement 4, 2020, Pages 504-506, ISSN 1130-8621, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enfcli.2020.03.011>.

¹⁶ Alexandre Erler (2018) "Natural" Athletic Performance or a Level Playing Field? You Can't Have Both, *The American Journal of Bioethics*, 18:6, 30-31, DOI: [10.1080/15265161.2018.1459945](https://doi.org/10.1080/15265161.2018.1459945)

¹⁷ Potulski J. Criminal liability for doping in sport. *Balt J Health Phys Act*. 2019; Suppl 11(1): 1-8. doi: [10.29359/BJHPA.2019.Suppl.11.1.01](https://doi.org/10.29359/BJHPA.2019.Suppl.11.1.01)

disputes between athletes and their sponsors or teams. These contractual obligations form the basis of legal battles that extend far beyond the confines of the sports field. An Anti-Doping Rule Violation (ADRV) that results in a ban will have a big financial effect on the individual involved. This includes the need for athletes and Athlete Support Personnel to repay cash awards or financial penalties. Doping also has additional detrimental effects, such as breached agreements and sponsorship agreements, wasted money from the government, subsidies, and other financial assistance.¹⁸

Civil Liability.

Apart from facing repercussions within the sporting world, athletes may also encounter civil liability. If a competitor suffers harm due to the actions of a doped athlete, such as an injury sustained during competition, the affected party might pursue legal action, claiming damages for the harm suffered. This could lead to lengthy and costly civil litigation, placing not only the doped athlete but also their entourage and supporting entities in legal jeopardy.¹⁹

Beyond legal consequences, doping raises ethical and moral dilemmas. The use of performance-enhancing substances undermines the integrity of sports, eroding the fundamental principles of fair play and equal opportunity. This moral quandary extends to the societal impact of promoting drug use as a means to achieve success, potentially influencing impressionable individuals to take risks with their health and well-being.

The legal implications of doping in sports are multifaceted and far-reaching. They extend from violating anti-doping regulations to potential criminal charges, breaches of contractual obligations, civil liabilities, and ethical considerations. As the fight against doping continues, addressing these legal complexities remains crucial to preserving the essence of fair competition and upholding the integrity of sports on both a national and international scale. The pursuit of clean and fair competition not only safeguards the principles of sportsmanship but also upholds the spirit of athletic excellence without compromise.

In conclusion, ensuring doping control in sports is a multifaceted challenge that demands a multifaceted response. A holistic approach that includes education, research, stringent enforcement, global collaboration, and ethical considerations is necessary to preserve the essence of fair play and integrity in sports. While the battle against doping may never cease entirely, continual efforts to strengthen anti-doping measures are imperative to uphold the spirit of true athletic competition.

References:

1. Teale, P & Scarth, James & Hudson, S.. (2012). Impact of the emergence of designer drugs upon sports doping testing. *Bioanalysis*. 4. 71-88. 10.4155/bio.11.291.
2. *Biol Sport*. 2014 Dec; 31(4): 251–259. Published online 2014 Sep 12. doi: 10.5604/20831862.1120931
3. D. (2012, August 1). *Micro-dosing: the new trend in sports doping*. The Hindu. <https://www.thehindu.com/sport/other-sports/microdosing-the-new-trend-in-sports-doping/article3710793.ece>

¹⁸ E. (2023, January 11). *Consequences of doping*. The European Olympic Committees. <https://www.eurolympic.org/clean-sport/consequences-of-doping/>

¹⁹ Davis, Calvin, A Critical Analysis of the Legal Effects of the World Anti-doping Code (July 11, 2014). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3418617> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3418617>

4. Horwath, H., & Horwath, H. (2020, January 3). *Blood Doping and EPO: An Anti-Doping FAQ | USADA*. U.S. Anti-Doping Agency (USADA). <https://www.usada.org/spirit-of-sport/education/blood-doping-epo-faq/>
5. *S5 Diuretics and other masking agents | SSI*. (n.d.). S5 Diuretics and Other Masking Agents | SSI. <https://www.sportintegrity.ch/en/anti-doping/prevention/education/mobile-lesson/s5-diuretics#:~:text=Definition,Prohibited%20List%20of%20the%20WADA.>
6. *Education and Training*. (n.d.). World Anti Doping Agency. <https://www.wada-ama.org/en/what-we-do/education-and-training>
7. Philip Hurst, Ailish King, Kelly Massey, Maria Kavussanu, Christopher Ring, A national anti-doping education programme reduces doping susceptibility in British athletes, *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, Volume 69, 2023, 102512, ISSN 1469 0292, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2023.102512>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S146902922300136X>)
8. Stanger, Nicholas & Whitaker, Lisa & Backhouse, Susan. (2020). Testing the validity and reliability of the doping willingness in sport scale. *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*. 30. 10.1111/sms.13683.
9. Nissen-Meyer, J., Skotland, T., & Boye, E. (2022, February 14). *Are doping tests in sports trustworthy?* *EMBO Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.15252/embr.202154431>
10. *Sachenbacher-Stehle Case Raises Questions about Supplement Use and Safety – FasterSkier.com*. (n.d.). <https://fasterskier.com/2014/07/sachenbacher-stehle-case-raises-questions-about-supplement-use-and-safety/>
11. Paragraph 2.1. of the Article 2 of the WADA Code 2023, https://www.wada-ama.org/sites/default/files/resources/files/2021_wada_code.pdf
12. *Europol and the World Anti-Doping Agency to tackle doping together | Europol*. (n.d.). Europol. <https://www.europol.europa.eu/media-press/newsroom/news/europol-and-world-anti-doping-agency-to-tackle-doping-together>
13. Levente Nagy, *Sports and the Ethical Implications of Performance Enhancing Substances*, <https://trivent-publishing.eu/img/cms/14-%20Levente%20Nagy.pdf>
14. A.M. Fadlih, A.F. Idham, A.I. Nugraha, M.F. Dongoran, *Effects of doping on physical and mental health of sports athletes*, *Enfermería Clínica*, Volume 30, Supplement 4, 2020, Pages 504-506, ISSN 1130-8621, [#">https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enfcli.2020.03.011.#](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enfcli.2020.03.011)
15. Alexandre Erler (2018) "Natural" Athletic Performance or a Level Playing Field? You Can't Have Both, *The American Journal of Bioethics*, 18:6, 30-31, DOI: 10.1080/15265161.2018.1459945
16. Potulski J. Criminal liability for doping in sport. *Balt J Health Phys Act*. 2019; Suppl 11(1): 1-8. doi: 10.29359/BJHPA.2019.Suppl.11.1.01
17. E. (2023, January 11). *Consequences of doping*. The European Olympic Committees. <https://www.eurolympic.org/clean-sport/consequences-of-doping/>
18. Davis, Calvin, *A Critical Analysis of the Legal Effects of the World Anti-doping Code* (July 11, 2014). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3418617> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3418617>